

Understanding of binding of a bis(imido)-bridged dinuclear cobalt(III) complex with *Calf thymus* DNA

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Abstract : The interaction of a bis(imido)-bridged dinuclear cobalt(III) complex with *Calf thymus* DNA (CT-DNA) was investigated by the absorption and emission spectral studies, and viscosity measurements. Absorption spectral studies showed only moderate hypochromism with negligible red-shift, and the intrinsic binding constant value of $1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ justifies that the present complex interact with CT-DNA in the groove region. The Stern-Volmer quenching constant (K_{SV}) value of $3.66 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ obtained from the ethidium bromide (EB) displacement assays supports the above fact. The groove binding mode of the complex is further established by the viscosity measurements.

Keywords : Dinuclear cobalt(III) complex, *Calf thymus* DNA, spectral methods, viscometry measurements, groove binding.

Introduction

The rational design, synthesis and characterization of small metal complexes, which can serve as probes for nucleic acid structure manipulation or can exhibit nuclease property, have attracted considerable attention¹⁻⁴. Especially, the unique spectral properties and coordination flexibility of transition metal complexes helps to tune the DNA binding and cleaving ability by changing the ligand environment⁵. The intermolecular non-covalent interactions are of fundamental importance for understanding molecular recognition phenomena and biological processes⁶. The natural biomolecule recognition of DNA relies primarily on non-covalent binding, i.e. (i) in a groove-bound fashion (minor groove or major groove) stabilized by hydrophobic, electrostatic, and/or hydrogen-bonding interactions and (ii) through an intercalative binding mode by the stacking interactions between the aromatic moiety and the DNA base pairs⁷. It is thus more reasonable to search for the suitable agents that recognize DNA through non-covalent interaction⁸.

Cobalt is recognized as an essential element widely spread in the biological systems such as cells and organs, and interaction of their complexes of various nitrogen donor ligands with DNA has attracted much attention⁹. In fact, cobalt chelates have been found to interact with

biological systems and to exhibit significant cytotoxicity¹⁰, and the effectiveness of many anticancer agents depends on the mode and affinity of their binding with DNA¹¹. In this regard, chemical modification of nucleic acid by transition metal complexes is of paramount importance for designing chemotherapeutic drugs which regulate gene expression and tools for molecular biology^{12,13}.

We have recently reported synthesis, structure and *cis-trans* isomerization of a novel photoactive dinuclear zinc(II) complex with an azobenzene linker, and their relative DNA cleavage abilities were critically discussed¹⁴. DNA binding and nuclease activities of cobalt(III) and iron(II) complexes with diimine ligands have also been reported¹⁵. In continuation of our research efforts, herein, I report the interaction of a bis(imido)-bridged dinuclear cobalt(III) complex (**1**, Scheme 1) with CT-DNA that was studied by electronic absorption spectra, fluorescence quenching studies and viscosity measurements.

Experimental

Synthesis and structure of dinuclear cobalt(III) complex **1** was reported elsewhere by us¹⁶. Chemicals such as tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris) were purchased from Aldrich and Alfa Aesar. *Calf thymus* DNA

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of the structure of dinuclear complex cation **1**.

(CT-DNA) and ethidium bromide (EB) were obtained from Sigma. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent or analytical grade and were used without further purification. UV-Vis spectra of the complex were measured using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-35 spectrophotometer with a 1-cm path-length quartz-cell. Fluorescence experiments were performed with a Hitachi F-4500 spectrofluorometer.

A concentrated stock solution of **1** was prepared in 20 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.5 and was diluted suitably with same buffer to the required concentrations for all the experiments. The electronic absorption spectral method was employed for the intrinsic binding of the complex to CT-DNA in 20 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). The purity of CT-DNA was checked by UV absorbance¹⁷, while the concentration of DNA was calculated by verifying the extinction coefficient of DNA solution at 260 nm of 6600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹¹⁸. Absorption spectral titration experiments were carried out by maintaining a constant concentration of the complex (50 μM) with varying concentration of CT-DNA (10–80 μM).

The competitive binding study of **1** to CT-DNA was examined by the fluorescence spectroscopy with EB-bound CT-DNA (5 × 10⁻⁵ M) in 20 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). The excitation wavelength of EB-bound CT-DNA was fixed at 510 nm and the emission intensity was measured at 602 nm. The effect on emission intensity was measured by varying the concentrations of the complex from 0 to 120 μM.

Viscosity experiments were carried out on an Ostwald viscometer at room temperature. The flow time for each

sample was measured three times with a reproducibility of about 4% using digital stopwatch, and an average flow time was calculated. The relative specific viscosity was calculated using the equation $\eta = (t - t_0)/t_0$, where t_0 is the flow time for the buffer alone and t is the observed flow time for DNA in absence and presence of the complex. Data are presented as $(\eta/\eta_0)^{1/3}$ vs ratio of the complex to DNA where η is the viscosity of DNA in presence of the complex and η_0 is the viscosity of DNA alone.

Results and discussion

The electronic absorption spectroscopy is the most common means to examine the interaction between metal complex and DNA. In general, the absorption spectra of a metal complex bound to DNA through intercalation exhibit significant hypochromism and red shift due to the strong stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore of the metal complex and the base pairs of DNA¹⁹. The intercalative binding strength is determined by the extent of hypochromism exhibited by the complex. The dinuclear cobalt(III) complex displays intense absorption bands in the UV-Vis region which are attributed to ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) transitions from amine/imine functional groups to cobalt(III) ion. Absorption spectral titration with a fixed concentration of complex **1** and varying amounts of CT-DNA shows that upon addition of an increasing amount of CT-DNA to the complex only a moderate hypochromism was observed (Fig. 1). The intrinsic binding constant (K_b) was calculated by the following equation²⁰ :

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + 1/K_b(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)$$

where [DNA] is the concentration of DNA in nucleotides, ϵ_a is the observed extinction coefficient for the ligand to metal charge transfer band at each DNA concentration, ϵ_f is the extinction coefficient of the free complex, and ϵ_b is the extinction coefficient of the complex when fully bound to DNA. The intrinsic binding constant (K_b) of the complex was found to be $(1.7 \pm 0.05) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$, which is much lower than that reported for classical intercalators²¹, indicating that complex **1** does not bind to DNA through the intercalation mode. This result is consistent with the structural features of the complex as the planar pyridyl groups are situated very close to metal center, and thus are incapable to intercalate classically with the adjacent base pairs of DNA. Here, the aromatic

Fig. 1. Absorption spectral changes upon addition of increasing amounts of CT-DNA to the complex in 20 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) at room temperature : Inset shows the plot of $[DNA]/\Delta\epsilon$ vs $[DNA]$.

pyridyl rings of the ligands in the cobalt(III) complex are likely to facilitate the formation of van der Waals contacts within the walls of groove or hydrogen bonds in DNA grooves. The value of intrinsic binding constant is comparable to those reported complexes where intimate associations of the complexes with CT-DNA were observed via groove binding mode^{22,23}, which is consistent with negligible red-shift associated with the spectral titration.

Excitation of the complex either in aqueous solution or in the presence of CT-DNA did not result in any fluorescence emission at the room temperature. Thus, competitive ethidium bromide binding studies were undertaken to gain support for the extent of binding of the metal complex with DNA. It is well known that EB can emit intense fluorescence in presence of DNA due to the strong intercalation between the adjacent DNA base pairs²⁴. The fluorescent light of EB-DNA system may be quenched by the addition of a second molecule if it intercalates with DNA base pairs and replaces the EB molecules. The degree of quenching of fluorescence intensity for EB-DNA system is usually used to determine the binding extent of the molecule to DNA. The fluorescence spectra of EB-bound DNA in absence and presence of the complex is shown in Fig. 2. The fluorescence intensity at

Fig. 2. Fluorescence emission spectral changes by the addition of increasing amount of the complex (0 to $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$) to EB-bound CT-DNA ($5 \times 10^{-5} M$) : Inset shows the plot of I_0/I versus $[complex]$.

602 nm shows a moderate quenching with the incremental addition of complex **1**, which is a consequence of the displacement of some EB molecules from the DNA. The quenching efficiency of the complex was analyzed by the classical Stern-Volmer equation²⁵,

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{SV} \times [Q]$$

where I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities in absence and presence of the quencher, respectively. K_{SV} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant, and $[Q]$ is the concentration of the quencher. The quenching constant K_{SV} is a measure of the quenching efficiency of fluorescence intensity by the complex to EB-bound CT-DNA, and is obtained from the slope. The K_{SV} value for the complex was found to be $3.66 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$ which demonstrates a weaker affinity of the complex to CT-DNA than that of EB. This is consistent with the above trend in DNA binding affinities obtained from the absorption spectral method. These results altogether support the hypothesis that the compound does not bind through the intercalation mode. The findings are very similar to the literature reported results where intimate association of the complexes to the CT-DNA through the groove binding mode is well established^{10,22,23,26}.

In order to further explore the interaction properties between the metal complex and the DNA, the relative specific viscosity of DNA was examined by varying con-

centration of the added complex. Viscosity is quite sensitive to molecular lengths that provide strong evidences for the DNA binding modes, especially in the absence of crystallographic and NMR structural data²⁷. A classical intercalating agent results in lengthening the DNA helix, as base pairs are separated to accommodate the binding ligand, leading to the increase of DNA viscosity. However, a partial and/or non-classical intercalation of ligand causes less pronounced or no change of viscosity in DNA solution. The plot of $(\eta/\eta_0)^{1/3}$ vs [complex]/[DNA] (Fig. 3) reveals a minor increase in the relative viscosity of CT-DNA upon addition of the complex which is lower than the compounds those prefer to bind with DNA through intercalation binding mode^{28,29}. This result is in agreement with the trend in DNA binding affinities obtained from the spectroscopic methods (*cf.* above), and also supports the possible groove binding nature of the complex. This slight increase in viscosity may be explained by the partial insertion of the complex in between the DNA base pairs, leading to a slight increase in separation of the base pairs and, thus an increase in overall DNA contour length.

Fig. 3. Effect of increasing amounts of the complex on the relative viscosity of CT-DNA at room temperature.

Conclusion

The interaction of a bis(imido)-bridged dinuclear cobalt(III) complex with *Calf thymus* DNA was explored. The intrinsic binding constant measured by absorption titration method is calculated as $1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ while the Stern-Volmer quenching constant is found to be $3.66 \times$

10^3 M^{-1} by fluorescence spectral method. These data support the non-covalently groove binding interaction with partial insertion of the pyridyl ring of complex **1** between adjacent base pairs on the CT-DNA duplex. The viscosity measurements assays also consistent with the above finding.

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